

CO₂-rich protoplanetary discs as a probe of dust radial drift & trapping

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Appendix C: Additional synthetic spectra

Appendix C.1: Later time examples

Figure C.1 shows how the input column density profiles have evolved by 0.1 Myr, when the pebble fluxes are at their peak (Fig. 3), and the impact this has on the resulting spectrum and column density fits thereto. The H₂O column density distribution no longer shows a peak inside the snowline as the enhancement has now spread throughout the inner disc. Since this is an example for Scenario 1, the same has happened for the dust (which is fully coupled to the gas inside the snowline), so the visible column density profile has changed negligibly. As a consequence, the H₂O spectrum also shows fairly little change.

Conversely, CO₂ has been hidden by the build up of dust inside the H₂O snowline. The enhancement seen at its snowline has begun to spread inwards, but there is little change in the dust abundance between the snowlines. Thus the visible column density of CO₂ has increased between the H₂O and CO₂ snowlines. The resulting increase in emission at larger radii and decrease in emission at smaller radii biases the CO₂ emission outwards, which manifests as a larger emitting radius retrieved from the slab fit. This gas is colder, which is reflected in the retrieved temperature from the slab fits and manifests most clearly in the spectrum as a shift in the peak of the P- and R- branches towards the Q-branch. Nevertheless, CO₂ outside of the H₂O snowline is still quite a poor emitter and so despite the contrast in visible column density of two orders of magnitude across the H₂O snowline, there is still a significant contribution from the hotter material inside, and the resulting column density is an average of the two limits. Overall, the CO₂ emission has weakened slightly compared to the H₂O at this particular time, which corresponds to a minimum in the retrieved CO₂ column density (Fig. 8).

For contrast we also include an example at 1 Myr as Fig. C.2. Here we see that since the CO₂ emission has become stronger with respect to the H₂O again, which is especially visible in the prominent ‘hot bands’.

Appendix C.2: Comparison with longer wavelength emission

Several works have pointed to the longer wavelength H₂O emission tracing a colder component (Banzatti et al. 2023, 2024; Temmink et al. 2024, e.g.) and found that the properties re-

trieved from slab fits change with the wavelength region on which the fit is performed (Gasman et al. 2023; Schwarz et al. 2024; Temmink et al. 2024). We therefore reanalysed the H₂O spectrum in the wavelength range of MIRI-MRS Channels 4A & 4B (17.70 – 24.48 μm) to see if any clear differences emerged.

Figure C.3 shows the spectrum in this region for the same smooth disc Scenario 1 model as Fig. 6, at the same time. The inset panel demonstrates that there is no excess in the lower excitation lines just short of 24 μm over their higher excitation neighbours. Such an excess has been observed in some discs (Banzatti et al. 2023, 2024; Temmink et al. 2024) and is typically fit with a temperature ≲ 180 K. Thus, it has typically been attributed to freshly sublimated H₂O as a result of pebble delivery. However, in our 1D model, only a narrow annulus is at these temperatures; a large emitting area - due to gas-phase H₂O in a warm, elevated, layer outside its midplane snowline - would be needed to make this component stand out but such structure is difficult to incorporate into a 1D model. 2D thermochemical modelling would be needed to determine the depth and extent of this layer and thus the resulting visible column density of water.

In Fig. C.4 we show that, likely in part due to the lack of any clear ‘cold excess’, there is no systematic difference between the temperatures retrieved from slab model fits to this spectrum as compared to those retrieved from the shorter wavelengths (e.g. Fig. 6). The temperatures are, to all intents and purposes, always the same, while the column densities are essentially always within a factor of two in all dust evolution scenarios explored in this work. As a consequence, we focus on the Channel 3 values in the main body of the paper.

References

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Fig. C.1. Synthetic spectra and retrievals as in Fig. 6 but for a later time of 0.1 Myr. The CO_2 is overall weaker with respect to H_2O and the P- and R- branches changed shape compared to 6.

Fig. C.2. Synthetic spectra and retrievals as in Fig. 6 & C.1. Note the different y-axis scale on the spectrum. This spectrum shows particular prominence of the hot bands over the P- and R- branches and the appearance of additional hot bands creating the bump overlaid on the P and R-branches.

Fig. C.3. Synthetic spectrum of H₂O in MIRI-MRS Channel 4A & 4B (assuming a distance of 140 pc). The inset panel shows the quartet of lines just short of 24 μm labelled with the energy of the upper level in the transition; if there were a ‘cold excess’ (c.f. [Banzatti et al. 2023](#)) the first and third lines would be stronger than the second and fourth.

Fig. C.4. Comparison of the temperatures (left) and column densities retrieved from the spectrum with a single slab model for Channel 3B/C (x-axis) and Channel 4A/B (y-axis) for the three different dust evolution scenarios.